

IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING METHODS IN THE PRACTICE OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS OF TEACHERS AND AS A RESULT

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Abstract. This article deals with professional pedagogy, the field of teaching each subject, the tasks, content, methods and organizational aspects of teaching, types of pedagogical approaches, types of observation and control of the lesson, the use of computer technology. the traditional teaching philosophy is described in detail.

Keywords: organizational vision, professional pedagogy, computer technology, pedagogical approach, and teaching philosophy.

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ МЕТОДОВ ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ПРАКТИКЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОГО МАСТЕРСТВА УЧИТЕЛЕЙ И, КАК СЛЕДСТВИЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье речь идет о профессиональной педагогике, области преподавания каждого предмета, задачах, содержании, методах и организационных аспектах обучения, видах педагогических подходов, видах наблюдения и контроля за уроком, использовании компьютерных технологий. подробно описана традиционная философия обучения.

Ключевые слова: организационное видение, профессиональная педагогика, компьютерные технологии, педагогический подход, педагогическая философия.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, didactics is understood as a pedagogical unit that scientifically substantiates the content, methods and organizational forms of teaching. In addition to general didactics, there are also private didactics or didactics called teaching methods in specific subjects. Their content determines the theoretical basis for the study and teaching of certain disciplines at certain stages of education.

The pedagogy of vocational education is divided into several sections, which cover the basics and important issues of vocational pedagogy, such as areas of vocational education, labor pedagogy, vocational didactics. They also study the social and psychological conditions of vocational education, the theory of vocational education and the law of vocational education.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

At present, a number of noteworthy works are being carried out in higher and educational institutions and professional colleges on the methods of teaching special subjects, the use of new pedagogical and information technologies in the teaching process, the problems of teaching methods.

Vocational pedagogy is a branch of general pedagogy that provides a range of theoretical and practical information about upbringing, education, and teaching. Professional pedagogy deals with issues related to the pedagogy of industry, production and labor.

Each subject is called a methodology, which is based on scientific information about the field of teaching, the tasks, content, methods and organizational form of teaching. The science of pedagogy studies the process of education and upbringing on the basis of their integrity and

unity. Didactics (theory of education) and theory of education are distinguished to clearly explain the essence of each of the two activities.

RESULTS

Every lesson should be a test of pedagogical skills, you should be satisfied with each lesson and learn something new. It should be noted that today the observation and analysis of the lessons of engineers-teachers and teachers of professional colleges is an important form of internal control. Lesson observation provides a good overview of the state of education, the rapid elimination of existing shortcomings and further improvement.

Every teacher needs to know the basics of didactics and organize activities based on them. There are different views on the definition of the subject of didactics. Differences of opinion are due to the fact that the methodological categories of didactics are not clearly defined.

There are many general principles in pedagogy that allow a teacher to improve his or her pedagogical skills. They are: awareness and activism; exhibition; structure and regularity; consistency; comprehensibility; scientific; unity of theory and practice; education - the unity of upbringing; education - the system of education and its length; principles of pedagogical technology.

DISCUSSION

The use of computer technology changes the traditional teaching philosophy, i.e. the 3rd participant in the learning process, the computer. Educators who are accustomed to traditional teaching technologies do not realize the importance and benefits of computer-assisted learning. Therefore, the use of computer-assisted learning technologies requires, first of all, the development of computer skills of educators, and the formation of an information culture. To use these technologies, first of all, it is necessary to improve the computer skills of teachers, to form an information culture in them. Regardless of the type of monitoring and control of the lesson, its main goal is to further improve the knowledge and skills of teachers, to improve the quality and effectiveness of the lesson. When analyzing the lesson, it is important not to talk about the shortcomings of the engineer-educator and students, but to provide pedagogical assistance in areas where they made mistakes, unknowingly, to help correct mistakes promptly.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, education quality management should focus on the organization of the teaching process based on information technology and the creation of conditions for effective pedagogical activity. The use of information technology will change the activities of teachers.

This is not about imparting ready-made knowledge to students using new teaching tools in a teacher's new pedagogical environment, but about developing them the skills to independently search and find new knowledge. The pedagogical approach is that education is interdependent.

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